

Open Alliance in Graphs

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Abstract: A defensive alliance in a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a set of vertices $S \subseteq V$ satisfying the condition that for every vertex $v \in S$, the number of v 's neighbors is at least as large as the number of v 's neighbors in $V - S$. For a subset $T \subset V, T \neq S$, a defensive alliance S is called *Smarandachely T -strong*, if for every vertex $v \in S$, $|N[v] \cap S| > |N(v) \cap ((V - S) \cup T)|$. In this case we say that every vertex in S is *Smarandachely T -strongly defended*. Particularly, if we choose $T = \emptyset$, i.e., a Smarandachely \emptyset -strong is called strong defend for simplicity. The boundary of a set S is the set $\partial S = \bigcup_{v \in S} N(v) - S$. An offensive alliance in a graph G is a set of vertices $S \subseteq V$ such that for every vertex v in the boundary of S , the number of v 's neighbors in S is at least as large as the number of v 's neighbors in $V - S$. In this paper we study open alliance problem in graphs which was posted as an open question in [S.M. Hedetniemi, S.T. Hedetniemi, P. Kristiansen, *Alliances in graphs*, J. Combin. Math. Combin. Comput. 48 (2004) 157-177].

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§1. Introduction

In this paper we study open alliance in graphs. For graph theory terminology and notation, we generally follow [3]. For a vertex v in a graph $G = (V, E)$, the *open neighborhood* of v is the set $N(v) = \{u : uv \in E\}$, and the *closed neighborhood* of v is $N[v] = N(v) \cup \{v\}$. The *boundary* of S is the set $\partial S = \bigcup_{v \in S} N(v) - S$. We denote the degree of v in S by $d_S(v) = |N(v) \cap S|$. The *edge connectivity*, $\lambda(G)$, of a graph G is the minimum number of edges in a set, whose removal results in a disconnected graph. A graph $G' = (V', E')$ is a *subgraph* of a graph $G = (V, E)$, written $G' \subseteq G$, if $V' \subseteq V$ and $E' \subseteq E$. For $S \subseteq V$, the *subgraph induced* by S is the graph $G[S] = (S, E \cap S \times S)$.

The study of *defensive alliance* problem in graphs, together with a variety of other kinds of alliances, was introduced in [2]. A non-empty set of vertices $S \subseteq V$ is called a *defensive alliance* if for every $v \in S$, $|N[v] \cap S| \geq |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$. In this case, we say that every vertex in S is defended from possible attack by vertices in $V - S$. A defensive alliance is called *strong* if for every vertex $v \in S$, $|N[v] \cap S| > |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$. In this case we say that every

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vertex in S is strongly defended. An (strong) alliance S is called *critical* if no proper subset of S is an (strong) alliance. The *defensive alliance number* of G , denoted $a(G)$, is the minimum cardinality of any critical defensive alliance in G . Also the *strong defensive alliance number* of G , denoted $\hat{a}(G)$, is the minimum cardinality of any critical strong defensive alliance in G . For a subset $T \subset V, T \neq S$, a defensive alliance S is called *Smarandachely T -strong*, if for every vertex $v \in S$, $|N[v] \cap S| > |N(v) \cap ((V - S) \cup T)|$. In this case we say that every vertex in S is Smarandachely T -strongly defended. Particularly, if we choose $T = \emptyset$, i.e., a Smarandachely \emptyset -strong is called strong defend for simplicity.

The study of *offensive alliances* was initiated by Favaron et al in [1]. A non-empty set of vertices $S \subseteq V$ is called an *offensive alliance* if for every $v \in \partial(S)$, $|N(v) \cap S| \geq |N[v] \cap (V - S)|$. In this case we say that every vertex in $\partial(S)$ is *vulnerable* to possible attack by vertices in S . An offensive alliance is called *strong* if for every vertex $v \in \partial(S)$, $|N(v) \cap S| > |N[v] \cap (V - S)|$. In this case we say that every vertex $\partial(S)$ is *very vulnerable*. The *offensive alliance number*, $a_o(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical offensive alliance in G . Also the *strong offensive alliance number*, $\hat{a}_o(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical strong offensive alliance in G .

In [2] the authors left the study of open alliances as an open question. In this paper we study open alliance in graphs. An alliance is called *open* (or *total*) if it is defined completely in terms of open neighborhoods. We study open defensive alliances as well as open offensive alliances in graphs.

Recall that a vertex of degree one in a graph G is called a *leaf* and its neighbor is a *support vertex*. Let $S(G)$ denote the set all support vertexes of a graph G .

§2. Open Defensive Alliance

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A set $S \subseteq V$ is an *open defensive alliance* if for every vertex $v \in S$, $|N(v) \cap S| \geq |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$. A set $S \subseteq V$ is an *open strong defensive alliance* if for every vertex $v \in S$, $|N(v) \cap S| > |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$. An open (strong) defensive alliance S is called *critical* if no proper subset of S is an open (strong) defensive alliance. The *open defensive alliance number*, $a_t(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical open defensive alliance in G , and the *strong open defensive alliance number*, $\hat{a}_t(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical open strong defensive alliance in G .

We remark that with this definition, strong defensive alliance is equivalent to open defensive alliance, and so we have the following observation.

Observation 2.1 For any graph G , $a_t(G) = \hat{a}(G)$.

Thus we focus on open strong defensive alliances in G . We refer to an $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set as a minimum open strong defensive alliance in G . By definition we have the following.

Observation 2.2 For any $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set S in a graph G , $G[S]$ is connected.

Observation 2.3 Let S be an $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set in a graph G , and $v \in S$. If $deg_{G[S]}(v) = 1$, then

$$\deg_G(v) = 1.$$

Note that for any graph G of n vertices $2 \leq \hat{\alpha}_t(G) \leq n$. In the following we characterize all graphs of order n having open strong defensive alliance number n . For an integer n let \mathcal{E}_n be the class of all graphs G such that $G \in \mathcal{E}_n$ if and only if one of the following holds:

(1) G is a path on n vertices, (2) G is a cycle on n vertices, (3) G is obtained from a cycle on n vertices by identifying two non adjacent vertices.

Theorem 2.4 *For a connected graph G of n vertices, $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) = n$ if and only if $G \in \mathcal{E}_n$.*

Proof First we show that $\hat{\alpha}_t(P_n) = \hat{\alpha}_t(C_n) = n$. Suppose to the contrary, that $\hat{\alpha}_t(P_n) < n$. Let S be a $\hat{\alpha}_t(P_n)$ -set. By Observation 2.2, $G[S]$ is connected. So $G[S]$ is a path. Let $v \in S$ be a vertex such that $\deg_{G[S]}(v) = 1$. By Observation 2.3, $\deg_G(v) = 1$. Then $G[S] = P_n$, a contradiction. Thus $\hat{\alpha}_t(P_n) = n$. Similarly, for any other graph in \mathcal{E}_n , $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) = n$.

For the converse suppose that G is a graph of n vertices and $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) = n$. If $\Delta(G) \leq 2$, then G is a path or a cycle on n vertices, as desired. Suppose that $\Delta(G) \geq 3$. Let v be a vertex of maximum degree in G . Since $V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ is not an open strong defensive alliance in G , there is a vertex $v_1 \in N(v)$ such that $\deg(v_1) \leq 2$. If $\deg(v_1) = 1$, then $V(G) \setminus \{v_1\}$ is an open strong defensive alliance, which is a contradiction. So $\deg(v_1) = 2$. Since $V(G) \setminus \{v_1\}$ is not an open strong defensive alliance, there is a vertex $v_2 \in N(v_1)$ such that $\deg(v_2) \leq 2$. If $\deg(v_2) = 1$, then $V(G) \setminus \{v_2\}$ is an open strong defensive alliance, which is a contradiction. So $\deg(v_2) = 2$. Since $V(G) \setminus \{v_1, v_2\}$ is not an open strong defensive alliance, there is a vertex $v_3 \in N(v_2)$ such that $\deg(v_3) \leq 2$. Continuing this process we obtain a path $v_1 - v_2 - \dots - v_k$ for some k such that $\deg(v_i) = 2$ for $1 \leq i < k$ and either $\deg(v_k) = 1$ or $v_k = v$. If $\deg(v_k) = 1$, then $V(G) \setminus \{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$ is an open strong defensive alliance for G . This is a contradiction. So $v_k = v$. If $\deg(v) \geq 5$, then $V(G) \setminus \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1}\}$ is an open strong defensive alliance for G , a contradiction. So $\deg(v) = \Delta(G) = 4$. Since $V(G) \setminus \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ is not an open strong defensive alliance, there is a vertex $w_1 \in N(v) \setminus \{v_1, v_{k-1}\}$ with $\deg(w_1) \leq 2$. If $\deg(w_1) = 1$ then $V(G) \setminus \{w_1\}$ is an open defensive alliance, a contradiction. So $\deg(w_1) = 2$. Since $V(G) \setminus \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k, w_1\}$ is not an open strong defensive alliance, there is a vertex $w_2 \in N(w_1)$ such that $\deg(w_2) = 2$. As before, continuing the process, we deduce that there is a path $w_1 - w_2 - \dots - w_l$ for some l such that $\deg(v_i) = 2$ for $1 \leq i < l$ and $v_l = v$. Since $\Delta(G) = 4$, we conclude that G is obtained by identifying a vertex of C_k with a vertex of C_l . This completes the result. \square

As a consequence we have the following result.

Corollary 2.5 *For a connected graph G , $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) = 2$ if and only if $G = P_2$.*

For a nonempty set S in a graph G and a vertex $x \in S$, we let $\deg_S(x) = N(x) \cap S$. So a set $S \subseteq V$ is an open defensive alliance if for every vertex $v \in S$, $\deg_S(v) \geq \deg_{V-S}(v) + 1$. Notice that this is equivalent to $2\deg_S(v) \geq \deg(v) + 1$.

Proposition 2.6 *For any graph G , $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) = 3$, if and only if $\hat{\alpha}_t(G) \neq 2$, and G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to either (1) the path $P_3 = u - v - w$, where $\deg(u) = \deg(w) = 1$ and $2 \leq \deg(v) \leq 3$, or (2) the cycle C_3 , where each vertex is of degree at most three.*

Proof Let G be a graph. Suppose that $\hat{a}_t(G) \neq 2$. If G has an induced subgraph $P_3 = u - v - w$, where $\deg(u) = \deg(w) = 1$ and $2 \leq \deg(v) \leq 3$, then $\{u, v, w\}$ is an open strong defensive alliance, and so $\hat{a}_t(G) = 3$. Similarly, if (2) holds, we obtain $\hat{a}_t(G) = 3$.

Conversely, suppose that $\hat{a}_t(G) = 3$. So $\hat{a}_t(G) \neq 2$. Let $S = \{u, v, w\}$ be a $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set. By Observation 2.2, $G[S]$ is connected. If $G[S]$ is a path, then we let $\deg_{G[S]}(u) = \deg_{G[S]}(w) = 1$. By definition $\deg_G(u) = \deg_G(w) = 1$. If $\deg_G(v) \geq 4$, then S is not an open strong defensive alliance, which is a contradiction. So $2 \leq \deg_G(v) \leq 3$. It remains to suppose that $G[S]$ is a cycle. If a vertex of S has degree at least four in G , then S is not an open strong defensive alliance, a contradiction. Thus any vertex of S has degree at most three in G . \square

Let G_1 be a graph obtained from K_4 by removing two edge such that the resulting graph G has a pendant vertex. Let G_2 be a graph obtained from K_4 by removing an edge, with vertices $\{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, where $\deg(v_1) = \deg(v_2) = 2$.

Proposition 2.7 *For any graph G , $\hat{a}_t(G) = 4$ if and only if $\hat{a}_t(G) \notin \{2, 3\}$, and G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to one of the following:*

- (1) P_4 , with vertices, in order, v_1, v_2, v_3 and v_4 , where $\deg(v_1) = \deg(v_4) = 1$, and $\deg(v_2)$ and $\deg(v_3)$ are at most three;
- (2) C_4 , where each vertex is of degree at most three;
- (3) K_4 , where each vertex has degree at most five;
- (4) $K_{1,3}$, with vertices $\{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, where $\deg(v_i) = 1$ for $i = 2, 3, 4$, and $\deg(v_1) \leq 5$;
- (5) G_1 , where $\deg(v_i) \leq 5$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$;
- (6) G_2 , where $\deg(v_i) \leq 3$ for $i = 1, 2$, and $\deg(v_i) \leq 5$ for $i = 3, 4$.

Proof It is a routine matter to see that if $\hat{a}_t(G) \notin \{2, 3\}$, and G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to (i) for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, 6\}$, then $\hat{a}_t(G) = 4$. Suppose that $\hat{a}_t(G) = 4$. Let $S = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ be a $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set. By Observation 2.2 $G[S]$ is connected. If $G[S]$ is a path, then we assume that $\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) = 1$ for $i = 1, 4$, and $\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) = 2$ for $i = 2, 3$. Now by Observation 2.3 $\deg(v_i) = 1$ for $i = 1, 4$, and $4 = 2\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) \geq \deg(v_i) + 1$ which implies that $\deg(v_i) \leq 3$ for $i = 2, 3$. We deduce that G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to (1). So suppose that $G[S]$ is not a path. If $G[S]$ is a cycle then $4 = 2\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) \geq \deg(v_i) + 1$ which implies that $\deg(v_i) \leq 3$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, and so G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to (2). We assume now that $\Delta(G[S]) > 2$. So $\Delta(G[S]) = 3$. Let $\deg_{G[S]}(v_1) = 3$. If any vertex of $G[S]$ is of maximum degree then $6 = 2\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) \geq \deg(v_i) + 1$ which implies that $\deg(v_i) \leq 5$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. So G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to (3). Thus we suppose that $G[S]$ is not complete graph. If $\deg_{G[S]}(v_i) = 1$ for $i = 2, 3, 4$, then by Observation 2.3 $\deg(v_i) = 1$ for $i = 2, 3, 4$, and $6 = 2\deg_{G[S]}(v_1) \geq \deg(v_1) + 1$, which implies that $\deg(v_1) \leq 5$. In this case G has an induced subgraph isomorphic to (4). The other possibilities are similarly verified. \square

Proposition 2.8 *For the complete graph K_n , $\hat{a}_t(K_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil + 1$.*

Proof Let S be a $\hat{a}_t(K_n)$ -set and let $v \in S$. It follows that $|N(v) \cap S| \geq \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$. So

$|S| \geq \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil + 1$. On the other hand let S be any subset of $\lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil + 1$ vertices of K_n . For any vertex $v \in S$, $\frac{deg(v) - 1}{2} \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1 \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$. Since $deg(v) = deg_S(v) + deg_{V-S}(v)$, $deg_S(v) - 1 \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$. This means that S is a critical open strong defensive alliance, and the result follows. \square

Proposition 2.9 $\hat{a}_t(K_{r,s}) = \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + \lfloor \frac{s}{2} \rfloor + 2$.

Proof Let V_r and V_s be the partite sets of $K_{r,s}$ with $|V_r| = r$ and $|V_s| = s$. Let $S = S_r \cup S_s$ be a $\hat{a}_t(K_{r,s})$ -set, where $S_i \subseteq V_i$ for $i = r, s$. For $i \in \{r, s\}$ and a vertex $v \in S_i$, $deg_S(v) \geq \lfloor \frac{n-i}{2} \rfloor$, where $n = r + s$. This implies that $|S| \geq \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + \lfloor \frac{s}{2} \rfloor + 2$. On the other hand any set consisting $\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ vertices in V_r and $\lfloor \frac{s}{2} \rfloor + 1$ vertices in V_s forms an open strong defensive alliance. This completes the proof. \square

Similarly the following is verified.

Proposition 2.10

- (1) $\hat{a}_t(W_n) = \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil + 1$;
- (2) $\hat{a}_t(P_m \times P_n) = \max\{m, n\}$ if $\min\{m, n\} = 1$, and $\hat{a}_t(P_m \times P_n) = \min\{m, n\}$ if $\min\{m, n\} \geq 2$.

Proposition 2.11 *If every vertex of a graph G has odd degree then $a_t(G) = \hat{a}_t(G)$.*

Proof Let G be a graph and every vertex of G has odd degree. First it is obvious that $a_t(G) = \hat{a}(G) \leq \hat{a}_t(G)$. Let S be a $a_t(G)$ -set and $v \in S$. By definition $deg_S(v) \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$. Since v is of odd degree, we obtain $deg_S(v) \geq deg_{V-S}(v) + 1$. This means that S is an open strong defensive alliance in G , and so $\hat{a}_t(G) \leq a_t(G)$. \square

So if every vertex of a graph G has odd degree then any bound of $a_t(G)$ holds for $\hat{a}_t(G)$. We next obtain some bounds for the open defensive alliance number of a graph G .

Proposition 2.12 *For a connected graph G of order n , $\hat{a}_t(G) \leq n - \lfloor \frac{\delta(G) - 1}{2} \rfloor$.*

Proof Let v be a vertex of minimum degree in a connected graph G . Consider a subset $S \subseteq N[v]$ with $|S| = \lfloor \frac{\delta(G) - 1}{2} \rfloor$. It follows that $V(G) \setminus S$ is a critical open strong alliance. \square

Proposition 2.13 *For any graph G , $\hat{a}_t(G) \geq \lceil \frac{\delta(G) + 3}{2} \rceil$.*

Proof Let S be a $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set in a graph G , and let $v \in S$. By definition $deg_S(v) - 1 \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$. By adding $deg_{V-S}(v)$ to both sides of this inequality we obtain $deg_{V-S}(v) - 1 \geq \frac{deg(v) - 1}{2}$. By adding $deg_S(v)$ to both sides of this inequality we obtain $\frac{deg(v) + 1}{2} \leq deg_S(v)$. But $deg_S(v) \leq |S| - 1$ and $\delta(G) \leq deg(v)$. We deduce that $\frac{\delta(G) + 3}{2} \leq |S|$. \square

Proposition 2.14 *For any graph G , $a(G) \leq \hat{a}_t(G) - 1$.*

Proof Let S be a $\hat{a}_t(G)$ -set in a graph G , and $w \in S$. Let $S' = S - \{w\}$, and $v \in S'$. It follows that $deg_{S'}(v) = deg_S(v) - deg_{\{w\}}(v) \geq deg_{V-S}(v) + 1 - deg_{\{w\}}(v) = deg_{V-S'}(v) + 1 - 2deg_{\{w\}}(v) \geq deg_{V'}(v)$, as desired. \square

Let $\Pi = [V_1, V_2]$ be a partition of the vertices of a graph G such that there are $\lambda(G)$ edges between V_1 and V_2 . Π is called *singular λ -bipartite* if $\min\{|V_1|, |V_2|\} = 1$, and *non-singular λ -bipartite* if $\min\{|V_1|, |V_2|\} > 1$.

Proposition 2.15 *Let G be a graph such that every vertex of G has odd degree. If $\lambda(G) < \delta(G)$ then $\hat{a}_t(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$.*

Proof Let $\Pi = [V_1, V_2]$ be a partition of the vertices of a graph G such that there are $\lambda(G)$ edges between V_1 and V_2 . Without loss of generality assume that $|V_1| < |V_2|$. This implies that $|V_1| \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. Since $\lambda(G) < \delta(G)$, we have $|V_i| \geq 2$ for $i = 1, 2$. As a result Π is non-singular λ -bipartite. If V_1 is not an open defensive alliance then there is a vertex $u \in V_1$ such that $|N(u) \cap V_1| < |N(u) \cap V_2|$. Then $\Pi_1 = [V_1 - \{u\}, V_2 \cup \{u\}]$ is a partition of the vertices of G and there are less than $\lambda(G)$ edges between $V_1 - \{u\}$ and $V_2 \cup \{u\}$. But $|\Pi_1| = |\Pi| - deg_{V_2}(u) + deg_{V_1}(u)$. So $|\Pi_1| < |\Pi|$. This contradicts the assumption $|\Pi| = \lambda(G)$. Thus V_1 is an open defensive alliance in G and the result follows. \square

§3. Open Offensive Alliance

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A set $S \subseteq V$ is an *open offensive alliance* if for every vertex $v \in \partial(S)$, $|N(v) \cap S| \geq |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$. In other words a set $S \subseteq V$ is an open offensive alliance if for every vertex $v \in \partial(S)$, $deg_S(v) \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$, and this is equivalent to $deg(v) \geq 2deg_{V-S}(v)$. A set $S \subseteq V$ is an *open strong offensive alliance* if for every vertex $v \in \partial(S)$, $|N(v) \cap S| > |N(v) \cap (V - S)|$ or, equivalently, $d_S(v) > d_{V-S}(v)$, where $d_S(v) = |N(v) \cap S|$. An open (strong) offensive alliance S is called *critical* if no proper subset of S is an open (strong) offensive alliance. The *open offensive alliance number*, $a_{ot}(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical open offensive alliance in G , and the *strong open offensive alliance number*, $\hat{a}_{ot}(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of any critical open strong offensive alliance in G .

If S is a critical open offensive alliance of a graph G and $|S| = a_{ot}(G)$, then we say that S is an *a_{ot} -set* of G . The next proposition follows from the definitions.

Proposition 3.1 *For all graphs G , $a_o(G) = \hat{a}_{ot}(G)$ and $a_{ot}(G) \leq \hat{a}_{ot}(G)$.*

Thus we focus on open offensive alliances in G .

Theorem 3.2 *For a graph G of order n with $\Delta(G) \leq 2$, $a_{ot}(G) = 1$.*

Proof Suppose $S = \{v\}$, where $deg(v) = \Delta(G) \leq 2$. Since for every $w \in \partial S$, $deg_S(w) = 1$ and $deg_{V-S}(w) \leq 1$. Therefore, $d_S(w) \geq d_{V-S}(w)$. So the result immediately follows. \square

Corollary 3.3 *For any cycle C_n and path P_n , $a_{to}(C_n) = a_{to}(P_n) = 1$.*

The following has a straightforward proof and therefore we omit its proof.

Proposition 3.4

- (1) $a_{ot}(K_n) = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$;
- (2) For $1 \leq m \leq n$, $a_{ot}(K_{m,n}) = \lceil \frac{m}{2} \rceil$;
- (3) For any wheel W_n with $n \neq 4$, $a_{ot}(W_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1$;
- (4) If every vertex of a graph G has odd degree then $a_{ot}(G) = a_o(G)$.

We next obtain some bounds for the open offensive alliance number of a graph G .

Proposition 3.5 For all graphs G , $a_{to}(G) \geq \lfloor \frac{\delta(G)}{2} \rfloor$.

Proof Let S be a a_{ot} -set and $v \in \partial S$. By definition for any vertex v of ∂S , $d_S(v) \geq d_{V-S}(v)$. By adding $d_S(v)$ to both sides of this inequality we obtain $d_S(v) \geq \frac{\delta(v)}{2}$. Also it is clear that $a_{to}(G) \geq d_S(v)$ and $\delta(v) \geq \delta$. This completes the proof. \square

Let $\alpha(G)$ denote the *vertex covering number* of G . That is the minimum cardinality of a subset S of vertices of G that contains at least one endpoint of every edge.

Proposition 3.6 For all graphs G ,

- (1) $a_{to}(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$;
- (2) $a_{to}(G) \leq \alpha(G)$.

Proof (1) Let $f : V \rightarrow \{a, b\}$ be a vertex coloring of G such that the number of edges whose end vertices have the same color is minimum. Let $O = \{uv : f(u) = f(v)\}$, $A = \{u : f(u) = a\}$ and $B = \{u : f(u) = b\}$. Without loss of generality assume that $|B| \leq |A|$. Suppose that B is not an open offensive alliance in G . So there is a vertex $v \in A$ such that $deg_B(v) < deg_A(v)$. Let $f' : V \rightarrow \{a, b\}$ be a vertex coloring of G with $f'(v) \neq f(v)$ and $f'(x) = f(x)$ if $x \neq v$. Let $O' = \{uv : f'(u) = f'(v)\}$, $A' = A - \{v\}$ and $B' = B \cup \{v\}$. Then $|O'| = |O| - deg_A(v) + deg_B(v)$. But $deg_B(v) < deg_A(v)$. We deduce that $|O'| < |O|$. This is a contradiction since $|O|$ is minimum. Thus B is an open offensive alliance in G , and so the result follows.

(2) Let S be a $\alpha(G)$ -set and let $v \in \partial(S)$. Since S is a vertex covering, $deg_S(v) \geq deg_{V-S}(v) + 1 \geq deg_{V-S}(v)$. This implies that S is an open offensive alliance, and the result follows. \square

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